

ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK-BASED SEQUENTIAL APPROXIMATE OPTIMIZATION FOR FREE FIBER PATH DESIGN IN VARIABLE-AXIAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an Artificial Neural Network–based Sequential Approximate Optimization (ANN-SAO) framework for the multi-dimensional design of curvilinear fiber paths in variable-axial composite laminates to maximize their fundamental natural frequencies. In each iteration, a feedforward neural network with four hidden layers, each composed of a linear transformation, layer normalization, SiLU activation, and dropout is trained on the current database of high-fidelity simulations. Early-stopping, weight decay, and adaptive learning-rate scheduling ensure both accuracy and generalization while keeping computational cost tractable. Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) is then applied to the ANN response surface to identify an exploitation point, whereas a companion Radial Basis Function based density function searches the sparsest region of the design space for exploration. The two candidates are evaluated with full Finite Element Analysis (FEA), their responses are appended to the training set, and the ANN surrogate is retrained. This cycle repeats until the maximum number of iterations is reached. Using this strategy, the number of expensive simulations is reduced while maintaining a global search capability. Numerical results for composite laminate plates show that the optimized curvilinear fiber architectures achieved by ANN-SAO yield substantial increases in the first natural frequency and favorable tailoring of the mode shape, thereby mitigating resonance risk and enhancing dynamic reliability. The proposed ANN-SAO framework thus provides an efficient, scalable, and accurate tool for vibration-driven design of advanced composite structures with free fiber trajectories.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) are composite materials consisting of carbon fibers embedded within a resin matrix. These materials exhibit high strength and high stiffness [1], making them increasingly favored in industries such as aerospace and automotive [2]. The anisotropic nature of CFRPs enables the tailoring of fiber orientations to meet specific mechanical requirements, offering design advantages over isotropic materials, albeit with increased complexity. Recent advancements in fiber placement technologies have further expanded this design space. Automated Fiber Placement (AFP)

enables high-throughput deposition of steered tows along non-straight trajectories, yielding complex, load-adapted laminates [3], while Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) stitches continuous fiber tows directly onto a substrate, realizing variable-axial paths with minimal waste [4]. Recent advancements in continuous fiber-reinforced polymer additive manufacturing techniques now enable the fabrication of continuous fiber-reinforced polymer composites with complex geometries and tailored fiber orientations, enhancing mechanical performance and expanding design possibilities for composite structures [5]. Previous studies have presented analytical methods for determining the natural frequencies and vibration modes of laminated plates with curvilinear reinforcing fibers. The results demonstrate that curvilinear fiber paths can significantly influence the dynamic behavior of composite structures [6-8]. To exploit this potential, researchers have applied a variety of optimization strategies. Early work focused on stacking-sequence or lay-up optimization of straight fiber laminates, using meta-heuristics such as particle swarm optimization (PSO) to maximize fundamental frequencies [6] and nonlinear lay-up optimization of variable stiffness composite cylindrical panels in free vibration using gradient-based methods, demonstrating enhanced fundamental frequencies through tailored fiber orientations [9]. While effective, these direct-search approaches require thousands of high-fidelity finite element evaluations and therefore become expensive when the design space expands to free (curvilinear) fiber paths.

The classical Sequential Approximate Optimization (SAO) framework encompasses various surrogate modeling techniques, such as Kriging, Radial Basis Function (RBF) networks, and Support Vector Regression (SVR). These methods are extensively applied in engineering optimization, particularly when dealing with computationally expensive numerical simulations, as they effectively reduce the number of function evaluations required [10]. More recently, artificial-neural-network (ANN) surrogates have exhibited higher approximation accuracy and better generalization than linear regression (LR), decision tree (DT) and random forest regression (RF) when learning highly non-linear composite behaviors, particularly for buckling and strength prediction [11]. Building on these advances, this study proposes an Artificial Neural Network-based Sequential Approximate Optimization (ANN-SAO) framework to optimize curvilinear fiber paths in variable-axial composite laminates. In each iteration of the ANN-SAO, an ANN surrogate model (response surface) is constructed, and its predicted optimum is taken as a new sample point for local refinement. To maintain global search coverage, a radial-basis-function-based density metric identifies sparsely sampled regions and guides the addition of exploratory sample points. Through these exploitation and exploration steps, the surrogate model's accuracy is progressively improved, facilitating the discovery of fiber path configurations that significantly enhance the structure's dynamic performance.

2 EXPRESSIONS OF CURVILINEAR FIBER PATHS BY RADIAL BASIS FUNCTIONS

As a first step, we describe how curvilinear fiber paths are parametrically represented using radial basis functions, which will serve as the design variables for optimization. To represent high-degree curvilinear fiber paths on a plane, a surface generated by radial basis functions (RBFs) is employed. This approach involves generating a surface using RBFs, through a linear combination of three Gaussian functions, as shown in Eq. (1).

$$f(x, y)_{surface} = \sum_{i=1}^3 w_i \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_{c,i})^2 + (y - y_{c,i})^2}{r_i^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

This approach can capture the shape of a surface with a high degree of flexibility. Here $(x_{c,i}, y_{c,i})$ represents the center point, and the parameter r_i influences the surface smoothness: larger r_i values yield flatter shapes, whereas smaller r_i values produce sharper peaks. Each Gaussian component is multiplied by a weight factor w_i and summed to form the surface, which means the fiber path can be controlled by adjusting the parameters $x_{c,i}, y_{c,i}, r_i$ and w_i (where $i = 1, 2, 3$), the fiber path can be flexibly controlled (Fig. 1a). The contour lines of this RBF-generated surface define the nominal fiber paths. To ensure the path is manufacturable via the TFP process, the tool's vertical (z -axis) movement is modulated according to the fiber tow overlap rate α (Eq. 2), as illustrated in Fig. 1b.

$$\alpha = \frac{w_f - d}{w_f} \quad (2)$$

Where w_f is the width of a single fiber and d is the spacing of the centerline of the fiber tow. These contour lines are then discretized into segments using the curve's gradient from Eq. (3) to determine each segment's slope relative to the element centroid. This discretization facilitates their expression in a finite element model, as shown in Fig. 1c.

$$\theta_e = \text{Tan}^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial f / \partial y}{\partial f / \partial x} \right) \Big|_{x=x_e, y=y_e} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: (a) Surface defined by three Gaussian functions; (b) adjusted fiber path considering fiber wots overlap; (c) discretized contour lines on a 20×20 FE mesh.

The natural frequencies of the composite laminate were determined through a structured computational workflow. Initially, ANSYS software was utilized to design the structural geometry, providing essential model parameters such as element count, nodal coordinates, and node numbering. Subsequently, Python scripts integrated the fiber orientation angles for each element into ANSYS Mechanical APDL to perform modal analysis. For visualization, the Matplotlib library was employed to graphically represent the fiber paths. This Python-based automation facilitated the execution of the aforementioned steps, streamlining the optimization process.

In the modal analysis, SHELL281 elements from ANSYS were employed. Each element comprises eight nodes with six degrees of freedom, suitable for analyzing thin to moderately thick shell structures. A 100 mm × 100 mm square plate was discretized into a 20 × 20 mesh, resulting in 400 elements. The laminate configuration, as depicted in Figure 2, consists of a symmetric eight-layer stack: [(TFP)₂/PW 45°/PW 0°]_s. This arrangement includes layers of Plain Weave (PW) and TFP, designed to be compatible with future fiber stitching machinery. The base material comprises two PW layers oriented at 0° and 45°, forming the foundational structure. Two TFP layers with identical fiber paths are then superimposed, exhibiting contoured patterns that reflect their customized fiber orientations, stitched onto the outer surfaces of the base layers. This alternating configuration results in a symmetrically arranged laminate, aimed at enhancing frequency characteristics through variable fiber orientations within the TFP layers.

Material properties are summarized in Table 1. The thickness of the Plain Weave (PW) layer is defined as 0.191 mm. For the TFP layer, the local thickness is computed as a function of the fiber distribution determined by the overlap rate $\alpha(x, y)$. Assuming the fiber tow has a thickness of t_f when there is no overlap, the thickness at a point (x, y) where the overlap rate is $\alpha(x, y)$ can be expressed as:

$$t(x, y) = \frac{t_f}{1 - \alpha(x, y)} \quad (4)$$

The spacing $d(x, y)$ between fiber tow at a point (x, y) is determined by the following relationship (Eq. 5):

$$\alpha(x, y) = 1 - \frac{|\nabla f(x, y)|}{|\nabla f|_{max}} (1 - \alpha_{max}) \quad (5)$$

Where $|\nabla f(x, y)|$ represents the local gradient magnitude of the fiber orientation function at position (x, y) , which is inversely proportional to the fiber spacing at that point. The quantity $|\nabla f|_{max}$

corresponds to the maximum gradient within the domain, occurring where the fiber tows are most densely packed, i.e., where the fiber spacing reaches its minimum. The maximum overlap rate α_{max} is set to 0.6. Substituting this into the thickness expression gives:

$$t(x, y) = \frac{|\nabla f|_{max}}{|\nabla f(x, y)|} t_{max} \quad (6)$$

Where $t_{max} = t_f / (1 - \alpha_{max})$ represents the maximum thickness corresponding to the maximum overlap condition. This formulation ensures that the TFP thickness varies spatially in response to fiber curvature and distribution, approaching the actual fiber stacking behavior. In Table 1, "L" denotes the longitudinal fiber direction, and "T" signifies the transverse direction relative to the fibers.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional view of the composite laminate showing the arrangement of TFP and plain weave layers.

Engineering constant		Plain Weave Layer	TFP Layer
E_L	[GPa]	37.7	103
E_T	[GPa]	37.7	9.04
ν_{LT}	-	0.3	0.3
G_{LT}	[GPa]	3.26	5.05
ρ	[kg/m ³]	1442	1295

Table 1: Material constants for Plain Weave layer and TFP fiber tow.

3 SEQUENTIAL APPROXIMATE OPTIMIZATION USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

3.1 Sequential Approximate Optimization

Sequential Approximate Optimization (SAO) is particularly effective for addressing complex optimization problems characterized by nonlinearity, multidimensionality, and computationally intensive evaluations. Unlike conventional metaheuristic methods such as PSO and GA, which operate by directly moving design variables and require many costly evaluations, SAO adopts a model based strategy. It begins by constructing a surrogate model or response surface, that approximates the objective function based on a set of strategically selected sample points within the design space.

The optimization process proceeds by identifying candidate optima on the surrogate surface. These points are then evaluated using the high-fidelity objective function, and the results are used to iteratively update and refine the surrogate model. This cycle continues, with each iteration improving the model's accuracy and predictive power. To ensure adequate coverage of the design space and prevent premature convergence to local optima, a density function is introduced. This function identifies sparsely sampled regions, guiding the addition of exploratory points to improve the global search effectiveness of the algorithm.

One of SAO's key strengths lies in its capacity to generate accurate surrogate models that effectively

approximate complex physical phenomena. This makes it especially suitable for applications where direct evaluations are expensive, such as finite element analyses or experimental testing. By leveraging surrogate modelling, SAO significantly reduces the number of high-cost simulations required to identify optimal solutions [10]. A typical SAO framework follows a structured sequence of steps, as outlined in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Workflow of the proposed Sequential Approximate Optimization framework.

In this study, a Sequential Approximate Optimization (SAO) framework is proposed using ANN as surrogate models. Initial sampling points are generated via Sobol sequences to ensure a well-distributed and space-filling design. An ANN-based response surface is then constructed to capture the nonlinear relationship between design variables and the objective function. To explore promising regions, the surrogate is optimized using the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES), and the obtained optimum is evaluated with the high-fidelity model. Simultaneously, a sampling density function is modeled using a RBF network, and PSO is employed to identify sparse regions in the design space, from which additional sampling points are selected. These new samples are incorporated into the dataset to refine both the surrogate and the density model. This iterative process continues until a predefined convergence criterion is met.

3.2 Artificial Neural Network

In this study, a feedforward Artificial Neural Network (ANN) with four hidden layers, each containing 126 neurons, is employed as the surrogate model to approximate the nonlinear relationship between the design variables and the objective function. The ANN architecture, training procedures, and implementation were adapted based on guidelines presented by Subramanian [12].

Specifically, for each hidden layer l , the pre-activation output is computed as:

$$\mathbf{z}^{(l)} = \mathbf{W}^{(l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}, \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, L-1, \quad \mathbf{h}^{(0)} = \mathbf{x} \quad (7)$$

Each hidden layer applies the SiLU activation function defined as:

$$\phi(\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{s} \sigma(\mathbf{s}), \quad \delta(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\mathbf{s}}} \Rightarrow \mathbf{h}^{(l)} = \phi(\mathbf{z}^{(l)}) \quad (8)$$

Layer normalization and dropout (rate = 0.1) are applied after each activation to enhance generalization and prevent overfitting. The final output of the network is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{W}^{(L)} \mathbf{h}^{(L-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(L)} \quad (9)$$

where $w = \{\mathbf{W}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\}_{l=1}^L$ denotes all weights and biases in the model. The ANN is trained to minimize the regularized mean-squared error:

$$E(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{w}))^2 + \lambda \sum_j w_j^2 \quad (10)$$

An Adam optimizer is employed, along with an adaptive learning-rate scheduler and early stopping. After each iteration of the Sequential Approximate Optimization (SAO) process, the ANN surrogate model is retrained using the expanded dataset, thereby maintaining its accuracy and currency with newly sampled data points.

3.3 Density Function

To evaluate the distribution of sampling points across the design space, a sampling density function $D(\mathbf{x})$ is constructed using the same RBF structure defined in Eq. (1), where each existing sample point is assigned a nominal value of 1:

$$\mathbf{y}_D = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T \quad (11)$$

The normalized inputs \mathbf{x}_D are obtained using the same scaling strategy as in the fiber path representation, with an expansion factor $\alpha = 1.2$ applied if necessary to ensure full basis coverage. The corresponding RBF weight vector \mathbf{w}_D is solved via regularized least squares:

$$\mathbf{w}_D = (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H} + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{y}_D \quad (12)$$

The density function is then given by:

$$D(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i^D h_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad (13)$$

By minimizing $D(\mathbf{x})$ using PSO, the sparsest region of the current design space is located, enabling exploration beyond already-sampled areas and supporting global optimization.

4 FIBER PATH OPTIMIZATION

With the ANN surrogate and sampling strategies defined above, we next set up the specific fiber path optimization problem including design variables and objective function. The design variables for the curvilinear fiber path are defined by the RBF parameters (Eq. 14), while those for the straight fiber path consist of a single fiber orientation angle (Eq. 15). The objective function in both cases aims to maximize the fundamental frequency, reformulated as a minimization task by negating its value (Eqs. 16 and 17).

The ANN-based response surface is optimized using the CMA-ES, configured with an initial standard deviation (σ_0) of 0.15 and a maximum of 300 iterations. For the density function surrogate, PSO is employed with a swarm of 500 particles, inertia weight $w = 0.7$, and acceleration coefficients $c1 = c2 = 2.0$, with 60 iterations. The ANN-SAO algorithm is configured to perform a total of 600 evaluations of the objective function, regardless of whether the fiber path is curvilinear or straight. The number of initial sampling points N_{init} is determined by:

$$N_{init} = 2 \times (n + 1) \quad (14)$$

where n is the number of design variables. The entire optimization process, including surrogate modeling and iterative updates, can typically be completed within approximately 100 minutes. The design variables and objective formulation are summarized in Table 2.

	Design variables	Objective function
Curvilinear fiber path	$x_{c,i}, y_{c,i}, r_i, w_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$) $-2 \leq x_{c,i} \leq 2$ $-2 \leq y_{c,i} \leq 2$ $0.5 \leq r_i \leq 4$ $-2 \leq w_i \leq 2$	$f(x_{c,i}, y_{c,i}, r_i, w_i)$ $= -(f^{1st\ frequency}) \rightarrow min$
Straight fiber path	$-89.9^\circ \leq \theta_{Fiber\ Angle} \leq 90^\circ$	$f(\theta) = -(f^{1st\ frequency}) \rightarrow min$

Table 2: Design variables and objective function formulations for the curvilinear vs. straight fiber path optimization.

The objective of this study is to optimize the fiber orientation of four TFP layers located at the outermost part of a symmetric eight-layer laminate using ANN-SAO. To ensure consistent material properties, the same TFP configuration is applied to both curvilinear and straight fiber paths. Boundary conditions are defined using 'F' for free edges. Fiber path optimization is carried out under all free boundary conditions to evaluate the effectiveness of the ANN-SAO framework.

5 NUMERICAL RESULTS

Under the FFFF boundary condition, the optimized straight fiber path exhibits a uniform orientation of -45° , achieving a fundamental frequency of 1038.42 Hz. Its mode shape reveals deformation primarily aligned parallel to the fiber orientation, with maximum displacement concentrated at the corners along the shortest fiber segments. In contrast, the optimized curvilinear fiber path forms concentric circular patterns centered at the midpoint of the plate, as shown in Fig. 3. This configuration enhances dynamic performance significantly, yielding a 24.41% increase in the fundamental frequency relative to the optimal straight fiber design. The mode shape exhibits that deflections are primarily confined to the four corners.

The detailed element wise distribution of fiber orientation and thickness resulting from the ANN-SAO optimization is depicted in Fig. 3. Although the thickness distribution under the curvilinear design exhibits slight spatial variation, the colorbar indicates that these fluctuations are minor. Notably, both designs share the same average thickness of 4.76 mm, confirming that the observed performance gains are attributed to fiber orientation tailoring rather than increased material usage. These results validate that the ANN-SAO framework effectively exploits smooth spatial variation in both fiber angles and layer thickness to optimize the fundamental frequency.

	Straight Fiber	Curvilinear Fiber	Difference
Fiber Orientation		—	
Natural Frequency	1038.42	1291.87	+24.41%
Mode Shape		—	
Thickness Distribution		—	
Average Thickness	4.76	4.76	0%

Figure 3: Comparison between the optimized straight-fiber baseline and the optimized curvilinear fiber orientation (green segments) under FFFF boundary conditions. Insets illustrate the corresponding mode shapes and thickness distributions.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study proposed an Artificial Neural Network-based Sequential Approximate Optimization (ANN-SAO) framework to optimize curvilinear fiber paths in symmetric laminated composites. By employing ANN to construct the surrogate model and integrating density-based sampling strategies, the method efficiently captured nonlinear relationships and improved optimization convergence. Compared with straight fiber configurations, the ANN-SAO optimized curvilinear paths significantly increased the first natural frequency under the tested boundary condition, indicating the effectiveness of tailored fiber steering for vibration performance.

Future work will focus on experimental validation of the optimized designs and extending the ANN-SAO framework to more complex composite structures and loading scenarios, further assessing its robustness and practical applicability in advanced manufacturing environments.

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